

CYBERSECURITY- DATA, PRIVACY, LIFE

Threats & Protection

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Introduction

During this pandemic crisis, the entire activity was moved online. Thus, the cybercrime activity has increased too. A question that is hard to answer is that: Are we prepared to this challenge? Not only the COVID-19 crisis has brought economic, political, cultural and social damage, but even the cyberspace has become an extremely sensitive area. The damage created by the black hat hackers has become more and more, visible,... the scamming, phishing has increased exponentially according to the latest data. All major cybersecurity institutes around the world are trying to fight against the daily attacks as much as is possible, and to find a solution that solve the problems before they occur. But one thing is certain, the fact that the best weapon against these attack is to inform the daily users.

Daily Attacks

Ever since the opening of the internet for civil use, it has always been a challenge in the security field. Cyberspace is a place where anonymity predominates, and because the cybercrime it is a world wide thing one of the main problem is also the legislative difference between countries. For this reason, in the military environment there is a great openness in collaboration with all countries for combat. For example, in the latest FBI statistics, at the end of 2019, 43% of Americans were victims of a cyber attack, as well as ENISA (European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) has recorded an alarming increases attack on civil and military field.

Thus, we can go deeper and see what occurs the criminality. Most cybercrime happens for 3 reasons or the one who causes damage can not value his potential in real life and thus shows his strength. Or the second option is that the motive of crime occurs to earn income, and the third reason is the combination of power-money.

Indifference and ignorance are also an important part in the security process of an information system. Where they appeared in the equation the security system will collapse. But it is in vain to have a robust system architecture if ignorance of the users prevails. In this field, every "component" is important, a user can have an super encrypted call channel but can be broken by the simple indifference that reflects at work or even at home. In other words, users (either civil and military) need to be instructed how important is the security and if they are victims of a cybercrime they need to report the incidence. Because every puzzle pieces, can help the authorities to combat another 20 crime. One thing to be noted is that the attackers have not just one victim but a multitude from different parts of the world or maybe just nationally.

Social engineering or so-called Dark Art is another major problem, this technique is a combination of psychological manipulation by sensitizing and constraining the target for the disclosure of either personal or confidential information. This technique similar to Divide Et Impera (Divide and Conquest) that was expanded by Niccolò Machiavelli caused many damage world wide because some target don't report to any authorities because they are afraid that the attacker will exploit the personal information and they better give any other confidential information (password, credit card number, ID, i.e).

Preventing the threat

A way to prevent the threat it is to inform the users about what they need to do in the difference situation and that they need to trust in authorities that they will make the best to combat the attacks. But for this they need to know about the issue, because you cannot prevent or attack something that doesn't know that exist.

Surfing on the internet has become a every day tool that help us in our work, to connect the people around the world. As well as any tool throughout history he can be a weapon of good or evil, construction or destruction. This depending on each person what do with tool.

Even the US Air Force has problems in cyberspace operations and states that "Our society and military are increasingly dependent on cyberspace. Cyberspace is a source of both strength and vulnerability for modern society." A major problem is also interception, although in the civil environment copper internet cables (being easy to intercept if there is physical access) have been replaced by fiber optics (they are harder to intercept due to the use of light rays) to provide greater security in intercepting data transmissions, but the problem reminded because if the target and the attacker are in the same public access point or in the same access point, the attacker capture the data. All this kind of attacks can be prevented if we have informed community.

In the cyberspace we have many factors that influence the future. For example Thomas Friedman has a very point of view about the idea to have a democratic cyberspace. In this equation the democratization and the globalization have pros and cons consequence.

In an open wide world we have a multitude of facts like the terrorist organization, mass media, religion, cultural and many other. The security in cyberspace is given by a multitude of facts. Thus a information found on the internet can either damage or help the society. Another notable influence is the fast developing of the technology.

Quantum Computing & Cryptography a future challenge of cybersecurity

This is a very close future problem because the quantum computing it is knowing on our door. And again, the question without an clear answer, *Are we prepared for this challenge? We have enough power to secure the world wide system?* In the past years, the research in this topic has increased and become a top priority to find a post-quantum cryptography for secure the data.

Cryptography has been a tool to secure confidential message/ data. From the Ancient Egypt (hidden message on tomb Khnumhotep II), the Bible (ATBASH), Sparta (Scytal) until the Charles Babbage (Vigenere Cipher), Arthur Scherebius (Enigma) and now day cryptography. Much of this ancient technique has evolved but the challenge of founding an ideal cryptosystem still exist. An it is much important now, when we speak about the security of a system and about the crucial impact that will have the quantum computing.

As we can see the cybersecurity still need to be improved and the daily users need to know what kind of threats are on the internet and how to deal with them, not to mention the human traffic, pornography and the drug traffic.

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